

D7.7

Report on Policy Advocacy

*Reporting period 01/09/2025
to 28/02/2026*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

**Funded by
the European Union**

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- 1 PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AU	Aarhus University
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CI	Creative Industries
DBR	Design-Based Research
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
KEA	KEA European Affairs
RT	Roundtable
WP	Work Package

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Summary of Deliverable

01

1 Summary of Deliverable

This report presents – as outlined in EPIC-WE’s Grant Agreement – a “summary of policy advocacy initiatives and presentation of key conclusions from the policy workshop. [It is to be] Published on the project website and distributed widely through EPIC-WE resource website, concluding events and elsewhere.” (GA p.26) It offers a comprehensive overview of the policy advocacy activities undertaken and in-progress by its consortium to date, highlighting how these efforts align with the project’s goals and intended impacts.

EPIC-WE is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation action that leverages a quadruple helix partnership – bridging cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth – in the pursuit of empowering young people as co-creators of culture through game making across a series of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs). Through a series of co-creative policy roundtables, their resulting briefs, and stakeholder events, the project has attempted to translate its on-the-ground experiences into policy recommendations aimed at strengthening cultural participation, young people’s engagement, and cross-sectoral collaboration and innovation in line with a broad swathe of E.U. policy priorities.

Key moments in our policy advocacy efforts have included the organisation of two policy roundtables in 2023 and 2024, and the publication of their corresponding Policy Briefs (Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2, with a third and final iteration set to be released soon) that distilled stakeholder insights into actionable recommendations. These recommendations address challenges ranging from diffused or fractured collaboration between needlessly distant sectors to the need for more youth-driven cultural initiatives. Additionally, a Policy Advocacy Workshop was held in Brussels in October 2025, convening an international group of policymakers, cultural practitioners, academics, and youth representatives alike. There, they discussed EPIC-WE’s results thus-far and worked in teams to decipher and iterate its most pressing and potent policy messages. This event further broadened the reach of EPIC-WE’s advocacy, ensuring that its results “reach a wide range of European CHI, CI and HEI actors, including the game industry, civil society organisations and youth” (find ga quote).

And so, in summary, EPIC-WE's policy advocacy efforts have created and sustained a rich dialogue between localised and grassroots cultural innovation experiences and supranational, institutionalised policy agendas. Going forward, these efforts are hoped to meaningfully inform policy frameworks, from E.C. initiatives to regional cultural and creative strategies, ensuring that the project's impact endures well beyond its lifespan. The proceeding text aims to provide a complete narrative of the methodology, activities, and outcomes of our policy advocacy efforts.

Introduction

02

2 Introduction

Cultural Game James (CGJs) are the practical cornerstone of EPIC-WE. CGJs are collaborative, culture-themed game creation events that games through and for culture inspired by cultural heritage, and EPIC-WE explores the potentials of these events as a method for strengthening European values, belonging and cultural participation. Through game-making activities, EPIC-WE equips youth with cultural-creative imagination and competencies to face societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency and imagination; it's what we call Empowered Participation.

From the outset, EPIC-WE's goals have included not only research and innovation outputs, but also a strong emphasis on policy advocacy. Indeed, extensive policy outreach has been built into EPIC-WE's operational architecture, an extensive effort towards informing and influencing outside-world practices and strategies in the broader creative sectors beyond gaming or cultural heritage alone. Of the project's four overarching objective, this commitment is most clearly reflected in the fourth, 'SCALE', with aims to "equip quadruple helix actors with knowledge, skills and policy instruments to exploit the potential of game-making with youth for the benefit of European society" (p.5). Under this objective, EPIC-WE has hosted a series of capacity-building workshops and roundtables with stakeholders to formulate policy recommendation supporting the uptake of EPIC-WE-style ecosystems across sectors. There have been already two completed Policy Briefs, with a third and final iteration on the way; a lively Policy Advocacy Workshop having taken place in Brussels some weeks ago; a marked and enduring presence of EPIC-WE at policy-related external events; and – at large – the engagement of over 300 key policy stakeholders throughout the project.

The policy advocacy activities reported here are thus a foundational stratum of EPIC-WE's ascent to real impact. Connecting the project's research (most practically the 12 CGJs across three partner countries) to broader EU-wide policy dialogues on culture, youth, and innovation, EPIC-WE has contributed substantial evidence on cultural heritage and creative industry policy in-line with major European initiatives and values, including:

- The New European Bauhaus (NEB): EPIC-WE’s cross-sectoral model, existing at the intersections of technology, visual aesthetics (through rich game illustration), it exemplifies NEB principles of sustainability, and inclusivity, and tech-driven innovation. By “removing barriers to collaboration between diverse actors and bridging creativity, culture, academia and youth” (Grant Agreement, p.20), the project advances NEB’s vision of a more sustainable future. Several EPIC-WE partners are concurrently NEB partners, and through these links, have showcased EPIC-WE resources and principles across the broader NEB ecosystem.
- Youth Engagement and European Values: The project responds to the urgent need for better youth involvement in cultural and civic life, especially in the wake of Covid-19. European policy documents (e.g. the EU Youth Strategy 2019-2027 and OECD Reports) stress that Europe’s resilient recovery “relies on the engagement of young people in the design of policies, recovery measures, public services and allocation of resources” (Grant Agreement, p.20), yet a lack of instruments to realise this ambition plague efforts. EPIC-WE offers a concrete model in response to this need by integrating young people as equal stakeholders in cultural institutions and creative projects, and in turn strengthening young people’s trust in those same institutions and the wider process surrounding them.
- Cultural Participation and Heritage: EPIC-WE directly addresses European calls to boost cultural participation and the societal impact of heritage. It treats games as a form of culture and heritage engagement, echoing the recognition that games can positively shape people’s worldviews and values, and thus resonating with European agendas that view culture as a driver of inclusion and democratic vitality. Our grant agreement argues that “culture serves as a critical role in promoting European values and supporting democratic society through artistic expression and creativity”, and our policy message only reinforces the importance of investing in such cultural participation.

This report is structured as a formal deliverable, offering an outline of EPIC-WE’s policy advocacy methodology, including the collaborative process used to generate policy recommendations. It goes on to provide a closer look at the activities and

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outputs so far, namely the policy roundtables, their resulting briefs, and the recent policy workshop, before synthesising the key policy recommendations that emerged from these encounters. Finally, this report will discuss the impact and alignment of EPIC-WE’s advocacy efforts with broader EU policy frameworks, and how they can be leveraged for longer-term impact.

Methodology

03

3 Methodology

EPIC-WE's policy advocacy at-large follows a participative, iterative methodology that is embedded in the project's conceptual pillars of design-based research (DBR) framework and the quadruple helix approach, adopting a multi-step policy development process that has been running in-tandem with its wider implementation. This approach ensured continuous and considered feedback between practice (i.e. game jams and capacity building workshops) and policy formulation, centring co-creation between the consortium and external stakeholders.

In term of this deliverable's methodology, its practical planning followed a staged process already described in D6.2, the Second Policy Brief. This process can be summarised as:

1. Review and scope
2. Desk Research and policy scan
3. Integration of policy insights and qualitative materials
4. Findings refined against EU priorities, stakeholder mapping, and relevance to EPIC-WE evidence
5. Consultation with reviewers
6. Iteration of a coherent narrative of the project's policy advocacy efforts

**Policy
Advocacy
Activities**

04

4 Policy Advocacy Activities

This section offers an overview of the main policy advocacy activities that have been carried out thus far in the EPIC-WE project (M1-34). The following table presents a snapshot of each event’s key events, participants, and outcomes. Subsequent passages go on to describe each activity in closer detail.

Activity	Timing & Format	Participants	Focus & Key Topics	Key Outputs & Outcomes
First Policy Roundtable (D6.1 – First Policy Brief)	M8; closed internal workshop	EPIC-WE consortium members and invited observers across the quadruple helix, including museum and heritage professionals, gaming and digital arts practitioners, academic researchers, and youth representatives	Identification of early challenges and opportunities in EPIC-WE activities; reflection on cross-sector collaboration; youth empowerment; and the role of games in cultural heritage	Foundation of EPIC-WE's policy advocacy work; development of the First Policy Brief (D6.1) with 8 foundational policy recommendations structured around communication and awareness, inclusion and diversity, co-creation and design thinking, and sustainability and scaling
Second Policy Roundtable (D6.2 – Second Policy Brief)	M21; hybrid format (in-person and online)	Consortium members and external stakeholders, including policymakers, Creative Europe programme advisors, Ministry of Culture representatives, youth councils, civil society organisations, and gaming industry leaders	Deepening and operationalisation of policy discussions emerging from Roundtable 1; cross-sector partnership models; youth inclusion; impact assessment; digital and open access; local and global engagement	Development of the Second Policy Brief (D6.2) with 11 detailed and actionable policy recommendations; consolidation of EPIC-WE's policy positioning and preparation for EU-level engagement
Policy Advocacy Workshop	M30; full-day in-person workshop in Brussels	34 participants representing European Commission services, cultural and creative sector leaders, academic experts, and youth representatives	Testing and validating EPIC-WE policy recommendations with policy-facing audiences; co-creative dialogue across the quadruple helix; cultural hubs as civic infrastructure; empowered participation; cultural game-making	Validation and refinement of EPIC-WE policy messages; strengthened EU-level visibility; thematic insights informing final advocacy steps; direct input into final policy advocacy actions and the EPIC-WE legacy event

Table 4a

4.1 Policy Briefing Roundtables

4.1.1 First Policy Roundtable (D6.1 – First Policy Brief)

This first roundtable set the foundation for EPIC-WE's advocacy work. Held in M8, at the midway point of the project's first year, it took shape as a closed workshop that primarily involved the project's consortium and invited observers from partnering networks). The decision to host this first session internally was deliberate: it allowed us to candidly and openly identify challenges from the project's early activities, as well as share speculations about limitations or best practices prior to engaging with a wider audience. Consortium members from across the helix attended, including museum and heritage sector professionals, gaming and digital arts creative professionals, academic researchers, and youth representatives. This rich diversity enabled what was dubbed a '360-degree perspective', despite the event remaining internal.

The agenda was structured around broad guiding questions aimed at uncovering both obstacles and opportunities encountered so far. Key topics included:

- Challenges in cross-sector collaboration
- Empowering youth voices
- Games for cultural heritage

Following the roundtable, the team compiled the First Policy Brief (D6.1). This brief presented eight policy recommendations. While the full list is available in D6.1, the key recommendations can be summarised under four themes:

- Enhancing communications and awareness
- Strengthening Inclusion and Diversity
- Integrating Design Thinking and Co-Creative Processes
- Sustaining and Scaling Initiatives

Given that the evidence was in its early stages, these recommendations were introduced at a foundationally, in broad strokes. Presented as 'key takeaways', it was

understood that they would be revisited, refined and expanded later. Fig. 2 (from D6.1) illustrates the major categories of recommendations from the first roundtable through a graphical abstract:

The first Policy Brief was then shared on the project website, uploaded to Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/13882418>), and disseminated widely across our consortium's networks. It served as a solid base for the project's subsequent policy advocacy efforts, as well as acting as a signal to stakeholders that EPIC-WE had policy on its radar and would be developing these core ideas.

4.1.2 Second Policy Roundtable (D6.2 – Second Policy Brief)

Building on that initial event, the second policy roundtable marked a significant upward trajectory in terms of both external engagement and depth of discussion. Conducted in M21, this roundtable adopted a hybrid format, featuring a core in-person workshop, with additional stakeholders joining online. This enabled broad participation across Europe, with the invitation list combining project members and external stakeholders selected based on their relevant expertise and influence. Amongst the attendees were a senior advisor from a Creative Europe programme office, a policy officer from a national Ministry of Culture, leaders from a youth council, civil society cultural organisations, and gaming industry professionals (including the director of a game developers' association). Through this richly diverse participant makeup, the quadruple helix model was entirely represented, and furthered by a layer of specialised policy insight. As a result, the second roundtable could take the shape of a deeper dive into issues that emerged from the first brief and subsequent project progress. Lines of discussion included:

- Cross-sector Partnership Models
- Youth Empowerment and Inclusion
- Impact Assessment of Cultural Projects
- Digital and Open Access
- Local vs. Glocal Engagement

By the end of Roundtable 2, there was a palpable sense that what had emerged from the first round has been concretised, with recommendations now more actionable and potent. The presence of policymakers and institutional representatives ensured that ideas were framed in terms of implementable actions and specific programmes, policy instruments, or funding schemes. The resulting Policy Brief (D6.2) was completed in early 2025, featuring 11 detailed policy recommendations. These can be grouped into themes and summarised as follows. These can be grouped into themes and summarised as follows:

- Public-Private Collaboration
- Inclusivity and Youth Engagement Sustainable Funding Models
- Impact & Assessment
- Digital Transformation & Accessibility
- Local & Glocal Engagement
- Cross-sectoral Learning & Innovation
- Open Research & Accessibility
- Expanding Roles of Cultural Hubs and Living Labs
- Environmental Sustainability

Collectively, these 11 recommendations from the Second Policy Brief provide a comprehensive policy advocacy roadmap for empowered cultural participation through games. Explicitly tied to EPIC-WE's findings and Europe's policy context, these recommendations are much more detailed than the first set, and have served as a key input for the final policy advocacy steps of EPIC-WE, including our workshop in Brussels.

4.2 Policy Advocacy Workshop

4.2.1 Concept and Objectives of the Workshop

In October of 2025, EPIC-WE convened for a Policy Advocacy Workshop in Brussels; a flagship event for its policy advocacy campaign and envisioned from the project's start to bring project results directly to EU policymakers' doorstep. It was titled 'Meeting in the Middle: Inclusivity and Empowerment through the EPIC-WE Model.'

The core objectives of the workshop were to:

- Test the relevance and clarity of EPIC-WE's policy recommendations with policy-facing audiences
- Foster cross-sector dialogue across the QH
- Translate project principles into concrete policy-relevant messages

4.2.2 Planning the Event: Logistical Framework, Speakers and Target Audiences

The workshop took place in October 2025 as an almost full-day event (9:30-16:00) event hosted at Brussels conference centre, l'Atelier des Tanneurs, using two dedicated spaces: one for plenary presentations and one for co-creative group work. The budget for this event was €5,000 in total, with an initial target of hosting up to 50 participants.

In-line with the quadruple helix framework, the attendee list, which ultimately amounted to 34 people, spanned multiple stakeholder groups:

- European Commission Policymakers
- Cultural and Creative Sector Leaders
- Academic Experts
- Youth Representatives

This diverse participation formed a microcosm of the quadruple helix at an E.U. policy level, with the workshop showcasing the first two policy briefs, influencing discussions and setting scene for our final policy advocacy discussions in the run-up to EPIC-WE's final conference.

4.2.3 During the Event: Speakers, Discussions and Cross-Sector Dialogue

The workshop began with an opening address from Maciej Szymanowicz, a Policy Officer at the Commission's DG CONNECT. Szymanowicz shared a policy perspective, situation EPIC-WE within broader EU digital games and innovation agendas. This was followed by EPIC-WE's Coordinator Rikke Toft Nørgård (Aarhus University), who presented *'EPIC-WE in brief: What is EPIC-WE? And how does the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub Model work? 5 Core Concepts'*. This session presented the project's core objectives, Design-Based Research Approach, and the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub Model. Then, Rasmus Wiinstedt Tscherning, CEO of the Creative Business Network (CBN) and WP6 Leader, introduced *'EPIC-WE and its policy dimension. An overview of EPIC-WE's policy dimension on a micro-meso-macro level'*, linking local experimentation to systemic policy change and grounding the audience with the question of what policy *is*, both to them at and at large.

After a coffee break, EPIC-WE Youth Advisory Board Member Elena Cheldaeva from the Hilversum Hub offered some reflections on her experience as part of the project, and engaging with the QHM. This partially interactive session reiterated the importance of young people as equal shareholders in cultural heritage, with Cheldaeva asking the audience to contribute their opinions on the importance of young people's perspectives to a digital mind map she had prepared. The group considered the various responses before Annakaisa Kultima, a researcher at Aalto University, took the floor. Kultima presented on *'Playing Together as Enabler of Social Resilience: Focus on Cultural Game Jam Dimension'*, giving us a glimpse into previous projects that she had worked on that adopted the game jam model and their enduring effect on herself and her network; a lively Q&A followed.

The policy workshop itself began after lunch. Led by Rikke Toft Nørgård, this co-creative session made use of a Padlet – a digital software similar to Miro or Mural – as a collaborative tool. The session had two rounds, with all participants grouped into mixed teams (the aim was for each team to feature a member from each strand of the quadruple helix). Across both Padlet rounds, several strong thematic insights emerged, including several about:

Cultural Hubs

Participants consistently emphasised:

- The importance of real-world real-life cultural hubs, rooted in existing “cultural homes” rather than newly created innovation spaces
- Cultural institutions as brokers of trust, spaces uniquely positioned as mediators between the public, private, and civic sectors
- The need to transform participation into co-ownership, with institutionalised decision-making processes that foster long-term engagement and responsibility
- “Meeting in the middle” as a practical principle, requiring shared methods and vocabularies across sectors.

Empowered Participation

Participants consistently emphasised:

- Participation must move beyond access, most pertinently for young people
- Youth advisory structures are effective when embedded structurally and not treated as add-ons
- Skills development and peer exchange are essential enablers of this empowered participation
- Inclusion and the mitigation of structural disparities depend on community-driven approaches rather than one-size-fits-all models.

Cultural Game Jams and Games through/for Culture

Participants consistently emphasised:

- Game-making should be recognised as a legitimate form of culture-making, not merely a tool or outreach activity
- Cultural game jams foster curiosity, creativity and cultural imagination, enabling young people to engage critically with both heritage and contemporary societal issues
- Value-sensitive game-making can support reflection on identity, belonging and European values
- The sector remains underfunded and under-recognised within traditional cultural policy frameworks, despite its growing societal prevalence.

Arthur Le Gall, Director of KEA European Affairs, closed the event with some brief parting comments that synthesised the key messages emerging from the day. Drawing on EPIC-WE's objectives and KEA's own experience with policy advocacy, Le Gall highlighted the need to bridge experimental cultural practice and formal policy frameworks, emphasising the importance of translating project-level evidence into actionable, policy relevant language. His remarks served as the transition to the day's end, and which point the group disbanded.

4.2.4 Impact of the Event

In the short term, the workshop validated EPIC-WE's policy directions and sharpened the language of its recommendations through direct engagement with policymakers and sector leaders. It also strengthened visibility of EPIC-WE as a credible interlocutor at the EU policy level.

In the medium term, the workshop has contributed to reinforced or newly forged connections across the quadruple helix framework; clearer articulation of policy-relevant concepts such as civic infrastructure and cultural game-making; concrete inputs feeding into the final phase of our advocacy efforts, including the final policy brief and the legacy event in February 2026.

Overall, our policy advocacy workshop has functioned as a pivotal moment in translating EPIC-WE's experimental research into policy-relevant knowledge.

Advocacy through Project Dissemination at External Events

05

5 Advocacy through Project Dissemination at External Events

In parallel to its formal workshops and policy briefs, EPIC-WE pursued policy advocacy through targeted participation in external events with a clear policy-facing dimension. These engagements enabled the project to disseminate its findings, methodologies, and values beyond the consortium and its primary networks. While the nature and format of these events varied, each contributed to expanding our policy advocacy footprint.

A particularly significant moment in this strand of our advocacy was EPIC-WE's participation in a closed technical meeting of the EU Internet Forum in November 2025, focused on recruitment in gaming spaces. The meeting addressed risks related to terrorism, violent extremism, and organised crime within gaming ecosystems. EPIC-WE was invited as an external stakeholder to contribute to the "Positive Interventions" track, presenting the project as an example of how such risks can be addressed through constructive, preventative approaches as opposed to solely through regulation or enforcement. Drawing on our use of the QHM and CGJs, we demonstrated how game-making and culture-making can foster belonging, thereby strengthening social resilience. Due to the confidential, high-security nature of the meeting, formal documentation cannot be shared; nevertheless, the invitation itself signals recognition of EPIC-WE as a meaningful contributor to sensitive EU-level policy discussions.

In addition, EPIC-WE contributed to a series of open policy adjacent events that allowed for wider dissemination of our advocacy. In May 2025, we participated in the online workshop, "Play, Learn, Innovate: Uniting Research, Education & Game Industry", organised by the Games for Culture Cluster. With Aarhus University as our representative, we introduced the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model from a higher education perspective. Later that month, we were represented at ekip's Policy Lab on Inclusivity in the Video Game Industry. Drawing on project insights, attendance at this event allowed us to translate our policy experience into policy-relevant reflections on diversity and equal access within the gaming industry.

In June 2025, we furthered our policy-oriented discussion points during a Discord Roundtable on Gaming, Wellbeing, and EU Policy. A multi-stakeholder exchange, the event brought together voices from industry, academia, civil society, and policymaking. EPIC-WE contributed reflections on youth mental health, positioning the project within emerging policy debates on platform responsibility. The project also had a strong presence at the European Youth Event (EYE) 2025 at the European Parliament in Strasbourg, where we hosted interactive panels exploring youth as value-sensitive game-makers, empowered cultural agents.

Taken together, these engagements extended EPIC-WE's policy advocacy beyond the remits of our primary networks, strengthened our visibility at the EU level, and contributed constructively to today's major debates surrounding European policy considerations.

Conclusion

06

6 Conclusion

As the EPIC-WE project enters its final phase, its policy advocacy efforts have crystallised into a clear set of messages stemming from a diverse community, a call to action on behalf of heritage sector practitioners, game developers, and young people alike. This report has attempted to narrate those efforts thus far linearly, demonstrating how this project has helped to bridge gaps between on the ground praxis and policy. Through structured roundtables, briefs, policy advocacy efforts at both purpose-held and external events, EPIC-WE has translated lessons learned in the field, particularly during CGJs, into insights for decision-makers. EPIC-WE's innovations can, thus, inform real-world change.

The findings and recommendations presented reaffirm that empowering youth and fostering cross-sectoral and multilevel collaboration in cultural projects is both possible and beneficial. By “meeting in the middle” – the ethos of the QHM wherein no single facet is prioritised – EPIC-WE has shone light on a means of co-creating solutions to cultural challenges. The policy recommendations, aligned with this ethos, urge stakeholders at all levels to support meeting place that support this co-creation, be it through funding, new governance models, or other formats of support. The results of a widespread adoption of the EPIC-WE model and ethos could lead to cultural heritage institutions more attuned to their audiences, the boundaries between praxis and academia becoming more blurred, and young people feeling valued as opposed to tokenised within cultural narratives.

Thus, the impact on European priorities is evident. EPIC-WE contributes to a vision of Europe championed by the New European Bauhaus through its cross-sectorality, as well as its outputs often tackling issues surrounding climate change and sustainability. It addresses the urgent need for closer youth engagement in shaping our shared future, answering calls from the EU Youth Strategy to involve young people in policy and civic life. It also highlights the role of games and playfulness as serious tools for education, cultural expression, and community building, hence enriching the EU's perspective on the digital industries' cultural contributions.

This report, D7.7, will be disseminated widely as the final consolidated account of EPIC-WE's policy advocacy efforts (bearing in mind that a third policy brief remains in the pipeline). This report will be shared across EPIC-WE's platform; namely, it will be hosted on our website and on Zenodo, and promoted across our social media channels (LinkedIn and Instagram). From thereon, the next steps will involve integrating final feedback from the concluding roundtable and conference (M36) and then focusing on sustainability. The consortium has already consolidated a number of memorandums of understanding with various organisations, connections that will certainly allow our advocacy efforts to endure. The resources produced across our project will also remain available under Creative Commons, acting as toolkits that any city or organisation can use to replicate the project's successes.

In conclusion, the EPIC-WE project has been more than a series of workshops and games; it has been a demonstration of a new participatory paradigm in cultural heritage innovation. Its policy advocacy efforts have ensured that this paradigm is recognised and can be scaled up. By empowering youth, deconstructing sectoral silos, and championing cultural participation, EPIC-WE contributes to a Europe that is culturally vibrant and socially inclusive. The project's legacy, carried forward through these policy recommendations and the people who shaped them, will hopefully be seen in future cultural and creative policies and programmes that embrace play.

Annex

Annex I: Policy Advocacy Workshop Padlet Outputs Round 1 & 2

EPIC-WE Policy Advocacy Workshop - Round 1

Instructions

↻ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 4:17AM

1. Press 'Add section' & write your names & press 'Publish' - this is now your section

☆ 0 0

↻ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 4:08AM

2. SELECT

- Look at the recommendations / principles for 'QH Cultural Hubs' and 'Empowered participation' (click pictures to the right)
- Select 1-2 recommendations / principles you find most promising or important from each core dimension (find them as text in comments)
- Press '+' under your section and insert your selection in the text field
- Press 'Publish'

☆ 0 0

↻ ☆ 0 6

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:44AM

Democratise cultural innovation by including citizens and users as core partner and innovator in the QH Cultural Hub

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:45AM

Form equal and transformative partnerships in cultural innovation transcending sectorial boundaries and methods

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:45AM

Institute meeting in the middle: all partners 'meet each other halfway' regarding vocabularies, ideas, methodologies, practices, and expectations

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:45AM

Practice co-creative cultural innovation for public good(s): prioritising public good(s) over purely economical solutions to ensure they are freely accessible for all

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:47AM

Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs: Rather than making new 'innovation spaces', partners use their 'cultural homes' to co-create with local citizens/users

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 4:47AM

Advance Empowered Participation in Culture: Prioritise innovation created through co-creation 'in the middle' enacting cultural imagination, agency, and respect.

QH CULTURAL HUBS

- 01 Democratise cultural innovation** by including citizens and users as core partner and innovator in the QH Cultural Hub
- 02 Form equal and transformative partnerships** in cultural innovation transcending sectorial boundaries and methods
- 03 Institute meeting in the middle:** all partners 'meet each other halfway' regarding vocabularies, ideas, methodologies, practices, and expectations
- 04 Practice co-creative cultural innovation for public good(s):** prioritising public good(s) over purely economical solutions to ensure they are freely accessible for all
- 05 Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs:** Rather than making new 'innovation spaces', partners use their 'cultural homes' to co-create with local citizens/users
- 06 Advance Empowered Participation in Culture:** Prioritise innovation created through co-creation 'in the middle' enacting cultural imagination, agency, and respect.

EMPOWERED PARTICIPATION

- 01 Establish Youth Advisory Boards:** To empower youth as creators to take active roles in shaping the direction of Cultural Game Jams, providing them with relevant scaffolding to support their self-directed goals and processes.
- 02 Establish mentorship programs and expert sessions across hubs:** provide participants with structured guidance and transdisciplinary insights.
- 03 Transform participation into co-ownership in Cultural Hubs:** Measure success not by research and innovation results alone, but by the extent to which participants feel respected, valued, and capable of co-shaping the narratives, practices, and futures they take part in.
- 04 Sustainability and empowered participation:** long-term partnerships, capacity-building, and cultural agency. Cultural hubs support this by embedding co-creation in local rhythms, grounding collaboration in everyday lived experience.
- 05 Support empowered participation in cultural heritage:** Use methods and support practices of Experience, Play, Imagine and Create (EPIC) in relation to youths' materialisations of cultural Worlds and Empowerments (WE) like the Cultural Game Jam Kit
- 06 A shared online space across Cultural Hubs:** This enables youth participants from different hubs and cultural worlds to exchange ideas, showcase prototypes, strengthen European creative networks, and explore local-global youth empowerment in culture and through game-making

↩ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 4:08AM

3. ARGUE

- Press '+' under your section
- Write a compelling title for your argument in the 'Subject field'
- In the text field below write a short argument for what makes your selected recommendations particularly promising or important: Why these? What is their potential?
- Press 'Publish'

↩ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 5:01AM

4. ADVOCATE

- Press '+' under your section
- Write a title that show how this connects to or calls for policies or priorities
- In the text field advocate: What concrete actions or policies are needed (or already in place) that might help turn the selected recommendations into reality?
- Press 'publish'

↩ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 5:16AM

5. READ - REFLECT - COMMENT (OR STAR)

Read the other groups' posts - comment on the posts that 'sparks a thought' or 'prompt input' that might support or nuance the post

And/or 'Star' the posts you find epic as you read along :)

GROUP 1

↩ AK 10/22/25 12:41PM

Annakaisa Kultima, Yelena van Kharitonova, Rasmus Tscherning

↩ AK 10/22/25 12:50PM

01 (QH)

↩ AK 10/22/25 12:51PM

Argue:

non-elitist, inclusive (in tandem to curated), because we need that for innovation

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ AK 10/22/25 1:00PM

Advocate:

Work on methods of participation: for instance developing platforms for the citizenship participants to engage with their peers, or ways and methods to help them (and others) in collaboration.

☆ 0 🗨 0

GROUP 2

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 12:41PM

Group 2 - the greatest

Virginia Vinesi
Arthur Le Gall
Noémie Krack

☆ 5.0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 12:53PM

QH Cultural hubs recos

04: CH institutions as brokers of trust - it's in their mandate to deliver "public" values (different economic actors)
05 = how to make it happen (complementary to R4)

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 12:53PM

Empowered participation recos

The big merger (industry concentration pun):

- Agency/ownership/inclusiveness, through YAB and sharing spaces/equal grounds (based on 01 and 03)
- Skills/knowledge/literacy/cty development and exchange, incl. info sharing (02 & 06)

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 1:13PM

Argue

04: CH institutions as **brokers of trust** - it's in their mandate to deliver "public" values (different economic actors)
05 = NESTING (care, built over time, comfy environment) how to make it happen (complementary to R4)

The big merger (industry concentration pun):

- Agency/ownership/inclusiveness, through YAB and sharing spaces/equal grounds (based on 01 and 03)
- Skills/knowledge/literacy/cty development and exchange, incl. info sharing (02 & 06)

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 1:13PM

Advocate

Can work well with local cultural policies (and interlinked local
pols - URBACT/INTERREG) - also connects to participatory trends
YAB = established practice in EU policies
Skills - pact for skills
Knowledge-sharing: ECCCH? ECHOES? New project?

☆ 0 🗨 0

GROUP 3

↩ DAPPER SNAIL 10/22/25 12:41PM

Elena and Julia

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ DAPPER SNAIL 10/22/25 12:45PM

QL cultural hubs

Advance Empowered Participation in Culture: Prioritise innovation created through
co-creation 'in the middle' enacting cultural imagination, agency, and respect.

☆ 0 🗨 5

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:11PM

Fostering ownership
- Building community by creating common ground

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:13PM

- Giving responsibility increase motivation

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:14PM

- Sustainable participation by institutionalized decision-making processes

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:16PM

- Increase of quality by need-oriented approach

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:17PM

Reduction of disparities

↩ DAPPER SNAIL 10/22/25 12:49PM

EMPOWERED PARTICIPATION

1. Support empowered participation in cultural heritage: Use methods and support practices of Experience, Play, Imagine and Create (EPIC) in relation to youths' materialisations of cultural Worlds and Empowerments (WE) like the Cultural Game Jam Kit
2. A shared online space across Cultural Hubs: This enables youth participants from different hubs and cultural worlds to exchange ideas, showcase prototypes, strengthen European creative networks, and explore local-glocal youth empowerment in culture and through game-making

☆ 0 🗨 1

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:39PM

2.
- it seems not practical as online presence is complicated to control
(moderator needed, clear structure, instructions)
- lack of personal interaction, emotional connection
- flexible communication channel saves resources

↩ DETERMINED PUFFIN 10/22/25 1:42PM

Fostering ownership

- Building community by creating common ground
- Giving responsibility increase motivation
- Sustainable participation by institutionalized decision-making processes

- Increase of quality by need-oriented approach
- Reduction of disparities

☆ 0 0

⇌ DETERMINED PUFFIN 10/22/25 1:42PM

Shared online space

- it seems not practical as online presence is complicated to control (moderator needed, clear structure, instructions)
- lack of personal interaction, emotional connection
- flexible communication channel saves resources

☆ 0 0

GROUP 4

⇌ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 12:47PM

Greta & Rickard & Jonathan

☆ 0 0

⇌ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 12:58PM

QH cultural Hubs

Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs: Rather than making new 'innovation spaces', partners use their 'cultural homes' to co-create with local citizens/users

☆ 0 0

⇌ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:01PM

Empowered Participation

03 Transform participation into co-ownership

☆ 0 0

⇌ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:19PM

Use what we have in a motivating, engaging way

Don't reinvent the wheel - the raw material is there! Get passionate about making a difference in the world - because you can. Find out the individual and collective roles, what we can do together.

☆ 0 0

GROUP 5

⇌ EDA&T 10/22/25 12:42PM

Eda & Rhian

☆ 0 0

⇌ EDA&T 10/22/25 12:47PM

Eda & Rhian - Develop real-world, real-life QH Cultural Hubs: Rather than making new 'innovation spaces', partners use their 'cultural homes' to co-create with local citizens/users

☆ 0 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 12:48PM

Eda & Rhian - Transform participation into co-ownership of Cultural Hubs

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 12:59PM

Argument 1: Community-building for culture, culture for community-building

Familiar places are more psychosocially potent, tangible spaces allow communities to participate and innovate in more intimate ways than online, and allow people to present themselves more wholly than when met with unfamiliar environments.

This ethos is also more sustainable in practice, more efficient financially, and in the urban/spatial context, a major potential contributor to social cohesion and neighbourhood sustainability. Cultural homes promote a sense of place and carry intangible cultural heritage within themselves. It enables newer and closer connections between locals and the lived heritage environment that surrounds them, deepening a community's sense of self.

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:04PM

Argument 2: In and Of Itself

Cultural Hubs are composed of and realised by their participants, and the co-creation stemming from this participant-led framework should be recognised, celebrated and formally supported.

Ownership can mitigate feelings of disenfranchisement amongst community members.

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:07PM

Calling for Inclusion

1. UN SDGs - 'Inclusively Living Together'
2. Cultural Heritage as a Driver of Local Regeneration.
3. Civic participation

☆ 0 🗨 0

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/2025 ↻

EPIC-WE Policy Advocacy Workshop - Round 2

Instructions

↻ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 5:06AM

1. Press 'Add section' & write your names & press 'Publish' - this is now your section

☆ 0 🗨 0

↻ RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD 10/22/25 5:06AM

2. SELECT

- Look at the recommendations / principles for 'Cultural Game Jams' and 'EGames through/for Culture' (click pictures to the right)
- Select 1-2 recommendations / principles you find most promising or important from each core dimension (find them as text in comments)
- Press '+' under your section and insert your selection in the text field
- Press 'Publish'

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↻ ☆ 0 🗨 5

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:38AM

Aim for cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment: transform game-making into an act of cultural imagination, where youth become active creators who engage, reinterpret, and contribute to the future of cultural heritage through game-making as culture-making

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:38AM

Foster cultural curiosity and creativity : By treating culture as an evolving, participatory experimental practice, these jams enable young people to actively shape cultural narratives and create meaningful cultural experiences.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:39AM

Cultivate an "epic we" through Cultural Game Jams: cultivate a sense of community and collective creativity that transcends the individual to foster an experience of becoming part of an "epic we" in cultural heritage

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:39AM

Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making : explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions, narratives, and aesthetics. Foster awareness of how games, through and for culture, can function as a method for cultural reflectivity, expression, and empowerment.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:39AM

Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation: dual focus on games through culture (exploring and incorporating cultural heritage as game-making material towards new interactive cultural expressions) and games for culture (imagining and enacting values, identities, and collective responsibility in culture and society)

CULTURAL GAME JAMS

- 01 **Aim for cultural participation, co-creation, and empowerment:** transform game-making into an act of cultural imagination, where youth become active creators who engage, reinterpret, and contribute to the future of cultural heritage through game-making as culture-making
- 02 **Foster cultural curiosity and creativity :** By treating culture as an evolving, participatory experimental practice, these jams enable young people to actively shape cultural narratives and create meaningful cultural experiences.
- 03 **Cultivate an "epic we" through Cultural Game Jams:** cultivate a sense of community and collective creativity that transcends the individual to foster an experience of becoming part of an "epic we" in cultural heritage
- 04 **Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making :** explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions, narratives, and aesthetics. Foster awareness of how games, through and for culture, can function as a method for cultural reflectivity, expression, and empowerment.
- 05 **Engage game-making as cultural innovation and interpretation:** dual focus on **games through culture** (exploring and incorporating cultural heritage as game-making material towards new interactive cultural expressions) and **games for culture** (imagining and enacting values, identities, and collective responsibility in culture and society)

↩ ☆ 0 🗨 6

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:40AM

Games through Culture: Tangible cultural heritage is a medium for experiencing, engaging with, imagining, and creating - cultural heritage transformations/reinterpretations

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:40AM

Games through Culture: Youth "jam" with cultural heritage within cultural environments such as galleries, libraries, archives, and museums, using the cultural assets there as concrete game-making material.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:41AM

Games for Culture: Youth become co-creative culture-makers by creatively reshaping cultural and societal narratives, issues, or experiences.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:41AM

Games for Culture: Game-making becomes a cultural or societal dialogic medium for exploring identity, belonging, citizenship and the role of European culture and values.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:41AM

Games as reflections and expressions of living cultural heritage: games as dynamic, living transformations, reflections and expressions of cultural heritage. Game-making as cultural practice that enables heritage to be preserved, reimagined, and transformed.

Rikke Toft Nørgård 10/22/25 7:42AM

Empower game-making as culture-making: Game-makers and game-players experience empowerment and belonging in culture through becoming active participants in shaping culture through engaging with the experiences, values, and worlds of games through/for culture

↩ **RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD** 10/22/25 5:06AM

3. ARGUE

- Press '+' under your section
- Write a compelling title for your argument in the 'Subject field'
- In the text field below write a short argument for what makes your selected recommendations particularly promising or important: Why these? What is their potential?
- Press 'Publish'

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↩ **RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD** 10/22/25 5:06AM

4. ADVOCATE

- Press '+' under your section
- Write a title that show how this connects to or calls for policies or priorities
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- Press 'publish'

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ **RIKKE TOFT NØRGÅRD** 10/22/25 5:15AM

5. READ - REFLECT - COMMENT (OR STAR)

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And/or 'Star' the posts you find epic as you read along :)

☆ 0 🗨 0

Group 1

↩ AK 10/22/25 1:26PM

Pikku Myyt:

Annakaisa

Yelena

Rasmus

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ AK 10/22/25 1:28PM

03: cultivate epic-we

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ AK 10/22/25 1:32PM

Advocate:

bring people together, provide opportunities for different people (battle also loneliness).

☆ 0 🗨 0

Group 2

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 1:22PM

Group 2 - still the greatest but more tired

Virginia Vinesi

Arthur Le Gall

Noémie Krack

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 1:34PM

Argue

02 with a pinch of 04:

Curiosity as a core value - from origin story to endgame: games as ways to create and convey powerful messages/impactful stories.

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ ALEGALL3 10/22/25 1:42PM

Argue 2

Games are a lot of things value-sensitive, dynamic, living processes and outcomes. It's value packed !

☆ 0 🗨 0

Group 3

↩ DETERMINED PUFFIN 10/22/25 1:19PM

Elena and Julia

☆ 0 🗨 0

⇨ DETERMINED PUFFIN 10/22/25 1:21PM

Foster cultural curiosity and creativity

By treating culture as an evolving, participatory experimental practice, these jams enable young people to actively shape cultural narratives and create meaningful cultural experiences.

☆ 0 🗨 5

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:25PM

- what is meaningful and for who

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:28PM

- Avoid simplification of cultures

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:29PM

- Cultural narratives shaped by community to avoid creating stereotypes

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:32PM

- chance to look from different angles on culture

Determined Puffin 10/22/25 1:32PM

- Chance to learn about different culture/ art

⇨ DETERMINED PUFFIN 10/22/25 1:43PM

Foster cultural curiosity and creativity

- what is meaningful and for who
- Avoid simplification of cultures
- Cultural narratives shaped by community to avoid creating stereotypes
- chance to look from different angles on culture
- Chance to learn about different culture/ art

☆ 0 🗨 0

Group 4

⇨ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:19PM

Greta, Rickard & Jonathan

☆ 0 🗨 0

⇨ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:24PM

Cultural Game Jams

02 Foster cultural curiosity and creativity : By treating culture as an evolving, participatory experimental practice, these jams enable young people to actively shape cultural narratives and create meaningful cultural experiences.

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⇨ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:27PM

Games through/for culture

03 Games for Culture: Youth become co-creative culture-makers by creatively reshaping cultural and societal narratives, issues, or experiences.

☆ 0 🗨 0

⇨ OBSERVANT CAPYBARA 10/22/25 1:39PM

Game making fosters curiosity and creativity, shapes and evolves culture

Freedom & openness inspired by curiosity, for creativity & culture to evolve.

☆ 0 🗨 0

Group 5

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:24PM

Eda Rhian & Allison

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:28PM

1. Practice value-sensitive and reflective game-making : explore how cultural heritage and values are embedded in and expressed through game mechanics, interactions, narratives, and aesthetics. Foster awareness of how games, through and for culture, can function as a method for cultural reflectivity, expression, and empowerment.
2. Empower game-making as culture-making: Game-makers and game-players experience empowerment and belonging in culture through becoming active participants in shaping culture through engaging with the experiences, values, and worlds of games through/for culture

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:33PM

Argument 1

Fostering awareness is crucial for niche sectors such as reflective European games. Value-sensitive games could be crucial for 'online generations' personal development and relationship with the digital space

☆ 0 🗨 0

↩ EDA&T 10/22/25 1:37PM

Argument 2

The game-making sector is a crucial facet of the contemporary cultural ecosystem but remains critically underfunded and faces underappreciation and under/misrepresentation in more 'high art' cultural circles. Empowering game-making as culture making formally & structurally helps ensure that the standards and ethics of european gamemaking remain driven towards positive change

☆ 0 🗨 0

<https://epic-we.eu/>

epicweproject@outlook.com

[/epicweproject/](#)